

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ACTIVITY ON CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART LI. CORRELATION OF THE CHARACTERISTIC WAVE-LENGTHS FROM DRUDE'S ROTATORY DISPERSION EQUATION AND ABSORPTION MAXIMA

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Both, one-term as well as two-term Drude's rotatory dispersion formulae, express equally well the optical rotatory dispersion of the compounds in the visible range (6708 Å-4358 Å). The characteristic wave-lengths (λ_c), derived from these equations, do not agree with the observed ultraviolet absorption maxima. The complex rotatory dispersion equations in some cases are almost equivalent to the one-term simple equations, with the second term contributing practically nothing to rotatory power; in other cases both terms are significant and the two characteristic wave-lengths obtained in these cases are nearer, but not equal to the absorption bands.

Thus the characteristic wave-lengths calculated from one and two-term rotatory dispersion equations are not the real absorption bands, but only the weighted average of the observed bands and those unobserved in the far ultraviolet.

The method of building up a two-term equation by substituting the two observed absorption maxima in place of two characteristic wave-lengths not only suffers from the defect that some hypothetical bands can be fitted in equally well, but also that it ignores other unobserved ultraviolet bands beyond the working range of the instrument.

The effect of chemical constitution on rotatory power and ultraviolet absorption bands is discussed.

The rotatory dispersion and ultraviolet absorption spectra of camphanoquinoxalines, camphanodihydroquinoxalines, *m*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -aminocamphors and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -aminocamphors are described.

The rotatory dispersion of an optically active compound can be expressed by Drude's formula :

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \sum \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$$

in which the summation covers all the absorption bands, and gives a series of similar terms, e.g.,

$$\frac{K'}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0'^2} \quad \frac{K''}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0''^2} \quad \frac{K'''}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0'''^2}$$

where K' , K'' , K''' etc. represent the rotation constants and each term is associated with an absorption band (wave-length λ_0). The observed rotations of optically active compounds are, in fact, accurately reproduced by expressions of this form, provided that the wave-length, λ , used in measuring specific rotations, $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$, does not lie in any of the absorption regions of the compounds.

In the present communication we have calculated both one-term as well as two-term rotatory dispersion equations for these compounds in ethyl alcohol to ascertain how far they agree between themselves and with the ultraviolet absorption maxima (λ_{max}) obtained by direct measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds studied here were prepared and purified as described earlier (Singh and Saxena, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 60).

The specific rotatory powers of the compounds were determined in several solvents at 35° in a 2-decimetre jacketed polarimeter tube for the visible region of the spectrum (6708 Å-4358 Å). Drude's one-term rotatory dispersion equations expressing the rotatory dispersion in this range are recorded in Table I, instead of the observed and calculated specific rotatory powers to economise space.

TABLE I
Dreide's one-term rotatory dispersion formulae.

Compound.	MeOH. [31.5] ^{**}	EtOH. [25.8]	Acetone. [21.5]	EtAc. [6.11]	CHCl ₃ . [5.2]	Benzene. [2.28]
1. <i>d</i> -Camphanquinoline	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35} = \frac{8.607}{\lambda^2 - (2693)^2}$	$\frac{8.592}{\lambda^2 - (2649)^2}$	$\frac{8.549}{\lambda^2 - (2797)^2}$	$\frac{9.472}{\lambda^2 - (2802)^2}$	$\frac{8.171}{\lambda^2 - (2736)^2}$	$\frac{9.5102}{\lambda^2 - (2901)^2}$
2. <i>m</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -imino- <i>d</i> -camphor	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35} = \frac{119.425}{\lambda^2 - (3919)^2}$	$\frac{125.421}{\lambda^2 - (3890)^2}$	$\frac{122.380}{\lambda^2 - (3939)^2}$	$\frac{118.596}{\lambda^2 - (3973)^2}$	$\frac{132.936}{\lambda^2 - (3814)^2}$	$\frac{126.188}{\lambda^2 - (4051)^2}$
3. <i>p</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -imino- <i>d</i> -camphor	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35} = \frac{197.46}{\lambda^2 - (4192)^2}$	$\frac{205.42}{\lambda^2 - (4205)^2}$	$\frac{217.16}{\lambda^2 - (4217)^2}$	$\frac{221.76}{\lambda^2 - (4260)^2}$	$\frac{228.42}{\lambda^2 - (4272)^2}$	...
4. <i>d</i> -Camphanodihydroquinoline	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35} = \frac{38.516}{\lambda^2 - (3082)^2}$	$\frac{43.105}{\lambda^2 - (3013)^2}$	$\frac{52.275}{\lambda^2 - (3221)^2}$	$\frac{54.183}{\lambda^2 - (3286)^2}$	$\frac{50.842}{\lambda^2 - (3298)^2}$	$\frac{59.254}{\lambda^2 - (3394)^2}$
5. <i>m</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -amino- <i>d</i> -camphor	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35} = \frac{34.386}{\lambda^2 - (2433)^2}$	$\frac{35.052}{\lambda^2 - (2545)^2}$	$\frac{39.984}{\lambda^2 - (2629)^2}$	$\frac{40.121}{\lambda^2 - (2738)^2}$	$\frac{41.340}{\lambda^2 - (2815)^2}$	$\frac{38.242}{\lambda^2 - (2952)^2}$
6. <i>p</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -amino- <i>d</i> -camphor	$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35} = \frac{19.01}{\lambda^2 - (3192)^2}$	$\frac{23.85}{\lambda^2 - (3185)^2}$	$\frac{31.46}{\lambda^2 - (2550)^2}$		$\frac{34.51}{\lambda^2 - (2578)^2}$	$\frac{32.49}{\lambda^2 - (2602)^2}$

* Figures in small brackets are characteristic wave-lengths in Å

** Figures in square brackets are the values of the dielectric constants of the solvent.

TABLE II
Drude's two-term rotatory dispersion formulae in ethyl alcohol.

Compounds :	d-Camphanoquinoline		d-Camphanodihydroquinoline		m-Phenylene-bis-amino-d-camphor		p-Phenylene-bis-amino-d-camphor	
	1.0000		1.0000		1.0000		0.5000	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	8.5703		13.6623		5.0428		23.7141	
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_{\lambda}^{35^{\circ}} \\ \lambda_{0} \end{array} \right.$	$\frac{0.0152}{\lambda^2 - 0.1620} + \dots$		$\frac{30.6237}{\lambda^2 - 0.06142}$		$\frac{30.1802}{\lambda^2 - 0.05628}$		$\frac{0.0104}{\lambda^2 - 0.49590}$	
	2853		3496		3138		3203	
Lines.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
6708	23.5	23.30	-120.5	-120.50	91.0	91.01	68.5	68.50
6438	26.0	25.78	133.0	133.45	100.5	100.19	76.5	76.15
6104	29.5	29.51	153.0	153.00	113.5	113.83	88.0	87.93
5893	32.0	32.32	168.0	167.86	124.0	124.00	97.0	97.00
5780	34.0	34.00	177.5	176.78	130.5	130.03	102.5	102.50
5468	39.5	39.50	206.0	206.21	149.5	149.51	120.5	120.82
5461	39.5	39.64	207.0	206.96	150.0	150.00	121.5	121.29
5209	45.5	45.25	239.0	237.48	169.5	169.50	141.0	140.58
5086	48.5	48.50	255.0	255.37	180.5	180.61	152.0	152.00
4800	58.0	57.73	307.5	307.50	211.5	211.56	185.0	185.60
4678	62.5	62.61	336.0	335.85	227.5	227.53	204.0	204.01
4603	66.0	66.00	356.0	356.00	236.5	238.50	216.0	217.13
4358	79.5	79.48	..	..	280.0	280.89	271.5	271.50

TABLE III
Absorption maxima (λ_{max}) and characteristic wave-lengths (λ_0) in ethyl alcohol.

S. No.	Compound.	Conc. (g./100 c.c.).		Dextro isomer.		Racemic isomer.		λ_0 from Drude's equation.	
		Dextro.	Racemic.	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	One-term.	Two-term.
1.	Camphanoquinoline	0.004	0.004	315 $m\mu$ 241	10371 24250	315 $m\mu$ 242	11333 26020	294.9 $m\mu$	402.5 $m\mu$ 285.3
2.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -iminocamphor	0.003	0.003	324 224	8094 29358	324 224	7286 27617	309.0	..
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -iminocamphor	0.002	0.003	347 228 208	11730 20604 23562	348 228 209	11390 19931 21143	420.5	..
4.	Camphanodihydroquinoline	0.002	0.002	343 232	4380 49680	344 232	4300 48502	301.3	349.6 247.8
5.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -aminocamphor	0.003	0.002	303 228	3726 27608	303 226	3458 25847	254.5	313.8 237.2
6.	<i>p</i> -Phenylene- <i>bis</i> -aminocamphor	0.002	0.00.2	323 256	3366 22114	323 255	3505 24142	318.5	704.2 320.3
	Phenyliminocamphor*	λ_{max} . { 324 226	ϵ_{max} . { 2318 8395	Phenyliminocamphors		λ_{max} . { 298 248 211	ϵ_{max} . { 1985 10530 5856		

* Singh and Saxena, this Journal, loc. cit.

The absorption measurements were taken in very dilute solutions of the substances in spectroscopically pure ethyl alcohol with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer up to the lowest limit (208 m μ) of the instrument. The absorption curves were plotted between wave-length and molecular extinction coefficients. Only a few of the curves (Figs. 1 and 2) have been given as illustration. The absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\max}$) have been tabulated (Table III) along with characteristic wave-lengths (λ_0), obtained from one-term and two-term Drude's equations for comparison.

DISCUSSION

The rotatory dispersion of all these compounds, when plotted between reciprocal of specific rotatory power $1/[\alpha]_{\lambda}$ and square of wave-length (λ^2), furnishes straight lines and can be expressed very well by Drude's one-term formula $[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$. The formulae for each of these compounds in several solvents have been recorded in Table I. There is a good agreement between the observed values of specific rotatory powers and those calculated from one-term Drude's rotatory dispersion equation. The differences are within the experimental error corresponding to a maximum difference of 0.02° in the observed angle of rotation. The characteristic wave-lengths (λ_0), which may be expected to be equal to the selective absorption bands, ($\lambda_{\max}$), of the compound, do not agree with any of the absorption bands obtained by direct measurements (Table III). These are thus not the actual absorption bands, but probably represent the weighted average of all the ultraviolet absorption bands.

d-Camphanoquinoxaline, *d*-camphanodihydroquinoxaline, *m*- and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-amino-*d*-camphors show two absorption maxima in the ultraviolet (between 400 m μ and 208 m μ) in ethyl alcohol (Table III). The two-term Drude's rotatory dispersion equation in the case of these compounds may therefore be expected to provide characteristic wave-lengths λ'_0 and λ''_0 equal to the two absorption maxima. These two-term rotatory dispersion formulae in ethyl alcohol are recorded in Table II. The values of specific rotatory power, calculated from these complex dispersion formulae, agree equally well with the observed values (Table II) as in the case of one-term formulae.

In the case of *d*-camphanoquinoxaline and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-amino-*d*-camphor it is found (Table II) that out of the two characteristic wave-lengths, one is almost equal to the characteristic wave-length of the one-term formula (Table I), while the other is high and the contribution of the partial rotation term containing it, to the rotation, is practically negligible. Thus, the two-term equations in these cases are reduced to one-term.

In the case of *m*-phenylene-*bis*-amino-*d*-camphor and *d*-camphanodihydroquinoxaline, however, both the characteristic wave-lengths of the two-term formulae also differ from the corresponding absorption maxima but by fewer units than do the characteristic wave-lengths from one-term formulae (Table III). These differences may be due to the fact that the two-term equation furnishes two characteristic wave-lengths, λ'_0 and λ''_0 , which are probably the weighted average of the two absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\max 1}$, $\lambda_{\max 2}$) observed in the spectral range, 400-208 m μ (208 m μ being the lower wave-length limit of the Beckman DU spectrophotometer) and other bands farther in the ultraviolet which have not been observed.

We have found similar divergences between the values of λ_0 and $\lambda_{\max}$ in other series of compounds (unpublished work).

Lowry and Hudson (*Phil. Trans.*, 1934, **A232**, 117) found, in the case of optically active xanthatates, definite divergences between absorption maxima and the characteristic wave-lengths calculated from the two-term rotatory dispersion equation.

The fact that the characteristic wave-length calculated from the one-term Drude's equation differs more from the absorption bands while a two-term formula provides the two characteristic wave-lengths, which are closer to the real absorption bands, shows that the two-term equation is definitely a step in advance, but that some more terms in Drude's equation corresponding to the remaining unobserved ultraviolet absorption bands (below 208 $m\mu$) are required for an exact agreement between $\lambda_{\max}$ and λ_{cs} .

The two-term formula of rotatory dispersion, containing four constants, would require four simultaneous equations for the evaluation of these constants. The calculations of the λ_{cs} from two (or more)-term equations being somewhat tedious algebraic operations, these have thus been generally avoided by chemists.

Recently Vasistha and Sarma (*this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 549) determined the rotatory dispersion of some aryl camphor- β -sulphonates and found that it could be expressed by Drude's one-term equation. They state that it can also be expressed equally well by a two-term equation,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \frac{K'}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0'^2} \pm \frac{K''}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0''^2},$$

when the two absorption maxima, $\lambda_{\max 1}$, $\lambda_{\max 2}$ (observed within the range 400 $m\mu$ - 208 $m\mu$) are substituted for λ_0' and λ_0'' . This method of treatment based on substitution is obviously erroneous; some arbitrary wave-lengths, other than the absorption maxima $\lambda_{\max 1}$, $\lambda_{\max 2}$, can also satisfy the equation, so that there is an agreement between the observed and calculated values of rotatory power. The argument based on substitution of absorption maxima for characteristic wave-length, thus, militates against this treatment. Moreover, there are very probably other absorption maxima farther in the ultraviolet (*i.e.*, lower than 208 $m\mu$) which cannot be observed with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

The correct rotatory dispersion equation covering all the ultraviolet absorption bands can only be evaluated if we know all the absorption bands, and not by substitution of a few bands registered by the instrument; bands below 208 $m\mu$ must also be taken into account.

The above mentioned treatment of these authors, which does not take into account all the ultraviolet absorption bands in the building up of Drude's equation for rotatory dispersion, is thus incorrect.

Chemical Constitution and Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra

The effect of conjugation and insulation of chromophores, as observed by Gillam and Hey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1170) in the case of polyphenyls and by Ferguson and Branch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1467) in the case of some aromatic imino compounds, is strikingly revealed by the absorption spectra of *m*- and *p*-phenylene-bis-iminocamphors in relation to phenyliminocamphor. The two bands at 324 $m\mu$ and 226 $m\mu$ of phenyliminocamphors (Singh and Saxena, *loc. cit.*) remain unchanged, as regards wave-length, in the case of *m*-phenylene-bis-iminocamphors with two insulated chromophoric systems, but the intensity of light absorption of both the bands is much increased (Table III). In *p*-phenylene-bis-iminocamphors (Table III), due to the same two chromophores being in conjugation, the 324 $m\mu$ band is shifted by 23 $m\mu$ towards longer wave-lengths and with much higher intensity. Such a remarkable shift is, however, not shown by the second band. The *para* isomer shows a third very strong band (208-209 $m\mu$) which is found to occur in some phenyliminocamphor derivatives.

Phenylene-*bis*-aminocamphors (*m*- and *p*-) show two bands which correspond with the absorption maxima of the bases determined by us :

	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	294 $m\mu$	923
	216	8154
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	312 $m\mu$	1123
	244	4158

These have, however, shifted towards longer wave-lengths by 9-12 $m\mu$ in the case of these compounds and have much higher extinction coefficients.

Camphanoquinoxalines show two bands at 315 $m\mu$ and 241 $m\mu$. The former is due to the pyrazine ring (Allan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 670). Both these bands of camphanoquinoxalines are markedly changed by the partial reduction of the compound to camphanodihydroquinoxaline (Table III).

Effect of Chemical Constitution on Rotatory Power

The rotatory power of *para* isomer is generally higher than that of the *meta* as in the case of *m*- and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-iminocamphors. This order is, however, reversed in the case of

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

corresponding amino derivatives, where the rotatory power of the *meta* isomer is higher than that of the *para* in all the solvents.

d-Camphanoquinoxaline shows relatively very low rotation (Tables I-II) which is due to the ring formation as in the case of *d*-camphoric acid, $[\alpha]_{5461}^{35} = 56.4$ and *d*-camphoric anhydride, $[\alpha]_{5461}^{35} = 0^{\circ}$ (Singh and Mahanti, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 378). On reduction of *d*-camphanoquinoxaline to *d*-camphanodihydroquinoxaline, the rotatory power is further decreased so that the latter becomes *laevo*-rotatory.

It is noteworthy to observe that the rotatory power of *d*-camphanoquinoxaline is almost the same in all solvents excepting that it is slightly lower in chloroform.

Absorption Spectra of Dextro and Racemic Forms

By the application of Roozeboom's melting point—composition method, the racemic modifications of camphanodihydroquinoxaline and *p*-phenylene-*bis*-iminocamphor have been found (Singh and Saxena, *loc. cit.*) to be *solid solutions*, whereas those of camphanoquinoxaline, *m*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -aminocamphors are true *dl*-compounds in the solid state.

The absorption spectra of the *dextro* and *racemic* forms (Table III) are, however, similar and the curves superposable in all the cases as illustrated (Figs. 1 and 2) in the case of *m*-phenylene-*bis*-imino- and -aminocamphors. No existence of a true *dl*-compound is thus revealed by the study of absorption spectra. This is due to the *racemates* (*dl*) having dissociated completely into their optically active and opposite forms at such high dilutions.

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